

ISic0474

Funerary inscription for Calbentius Motho

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

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Autopsy

2018.07.17 Prag

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Agrigentum

Place of origin (modern)

Agrigento

Provenance

Precise provenance unknown

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Agrigento, Museo Regionale Archeologico Pietro Griffo, inventory C1881

Physical Description

A slab of coarse bluish marble. Intact on all sides, but missing the top right corner. The sides are rough, the rear is finished and smooth.

Dimensions

Height 15.7 cm

Width 24.8 cm

Depth 2.4 cm

Layout

Five lines of latin letters with guidelines marked out for a sixth also. The text is centred, but slightly off the horizontal; hedera/interpuncts mark the line ends.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: 10-11 mm

Line 2: 11-13 mm

Line 3: 10-13 mm

Line 4: 11-13 mm

Line 5: 11-14 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: 11 mm

Interlineation line 2 to 3: 5-8 mm

Interlineation line 3 to 4: 5-8 mm

Interlineation line 4 to 5: 4-5 mm

Text

1. D(is) · M(anibus) ·

2. Calbentius Motho · vix(it) ·

3. annos · XXXX · Calbentia □

4. Fortunata · fratri □

5. suo □ fecit □

Apparatus

Text based on autopsy

Translation (en)

To the shades of the underworld. Calbentius Motho lived for 40 years. Calbentia Fortunata made (this)
for her brother

Translation (it)

Agli dei Mani. Calbentius Motho visse 40 anni, Calbentia Fortunata dedicò (questa iscrizione) a suo fratello

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491699

EDR 142396

EDCS 21900534

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. *Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum.* Berlin. At 10.7193 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650772>)

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